

School Mentors' Support to Student Teachers During Teaching Practice: University Supervisors' Chronicles

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 27, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: August 28, 2024</p> <p>Keywords : Chronicles; School Mentors; Support; Student Teachers; Teaching Practice</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13386098</p>	<p><i>This study was undertaken to explore the support school mentors offer student teachers during teaching practice. Using qualitative approach, this study employed document analysis; fourteen (14) reports from university supervisors were purposively sampled. The findings reveal that some school mentors support student teachers by assigning classes and preparing them for evaluation, some need to improve mentoring expertise, some do not have time for student teachers, some dump work on student teachers without support, some do not pay attention to critical issues needed by student teachers and others argue that they are employed to teach not support student teachers. The study concludes that some school mentors know their mentoring responsibilities while others are unwilling to offer support. This study recommends that school mentors be given incentives for supporting student teachers; they need to be workshopped about mentoring and made aware of the significance of mentoring. Higher education institutions should identify school mentors who are willing to support student teachers.</i></p>

Introduction

Do you know that very few school mentors support student teachers during teaching practice whereas most of them offer a very little or no support at all? Since teacher preparation programmes do not provide adequate insight that student teachers need, school mentors have to fill the gap by providing the mentoring support to student teachers (Polikoff, Desimone, Porter & Hochberg, 2015) to make up for the discrepancies that may arise from the dearth of knowledge and skills acquired via teacher educators. School mentors are subject teachers or subject specialists who guide and support student teachers in schools during teaching practice. As student teachers get to schools for teaching practice season, they rely on school mentors for mentoring so that they may be supported and guided on how to conduct teaching and learning activities effectively. Mentoring is a process whereby both experienced and inexperienced teachers engage in mutual learning (van Ginkel, Verloop, Denessen, 2016). For this mentoring to succeed, there should be a good mentorship whereby experienced and expert mentors support the less experienced mentees who are student teachers. The role of the school mentors includes helping, guiding and counselling the student teachers with their theoretical and personal advancement. School mentors are, therefore, key role players in the mentoring process. For this reason, Savage, Cannon and Sutters (2015) argue that for mentoring to achieve its excellence, it depends upon the generosity of mentors who make the journey with student teachers as they complete their teaching practice experience. Student teachers rely on the support they hope to find from school mentors so that they can acquaint themselves with the necessary skills and knowledge for teaching. Therefore, it is incumbent to establish the level of support that student teachers acquire from school mentors during teaching practice.

Teaching practice is meant to expose student teachers to the real experiences (El Kadri & Roth, 2015) of teaching and learning activities and for student teachers to receive guidance and support (Fletcher, 2000) to ease them through difficult school situations and other work-related issues. If student teachers are properly guided and supported, they may acquire proper knowledge and skills relevant for teaching. However, as argued by Tirivanhu (2014), some school-based mentors do not assist the student teachers to develop *teaching* or pedagogical skills. In other words, they do not support student teachers as expected. If school mentors do not offer the expected support to student teachers, the chances of student teachers not obtaining good marks during evaluations and not acquiring requisite skills are high. Therefore, the failure of school mentors to support and guide student teachers can have adverse consequences on the professional development of student teachers. Several studies have approached student teacher mentorship from such perspectives as its professional and pedagogical benefits (van Ginkel et al., 2016; Lamb et al., 2016), discord between university and school mentoring expertise (Tirivanhu (2014), perceptions of novice teachers on mentoring support (Clark & Byrnes, 2012), partners' perspectives on tripartite dialogue during field experience (Mtika et al., 2014), mentoring in a

cohort model of teaching practicum (Mukeredzi, 2017) and perceived possibilities and challenges of mentor teachers as mentors and teachers (Jaspers et al., 2014). However, there has been little agency accorded to the observations of university supervisors about the phenomenon when visiting schools where the phenomenon unfolds. This is the niche this paper endeavours to exploit so as to shed light on how the sampled university supervisors not only assess the phenomenon, but also how they reflect on their own agency as teacher educators.

The theoretical underpinning for this article was the human learning theory which assumes that the mentor guides the learners in discovering hidden knowledge with the aim of achieving self-actualisation (Maslow, 1968). For this theory, experience is the key phenomenon when studying human learning. Some theories that have been used to address the mentoring of student teachers are sociocultural theory, social exchange theory, social cognitive theory and scaffolded learning theory. However, these theories do not emphasise self-actualisation which requires student teachers to be actively involved so as to realise or fulfil their talents and potentials like human learning theory does. Student teachers may acquire experience through self-actualisation. It is for this reason, student teachers attend teaching practice in order to, amongst other things, acquire teaching experience through the help, guidance, support and exposure from school mentors. This theory advocates for self-actualisation which can enable the acquisition of experience. School mentors are expected to guide student teachers to discover new knowledge through teaching experience during the teaching practice. In line with this, this article aimed to explore the chronicles of university supervisors on school mentors' support to student teachers during teaching practice. These records may help to understand what exactly happens in schools amongst student teachers and school mentors in terms of support. Furthermore, this article highlights some views through the eyes of university supervisors on school mentors support to student teachers. This article was guided by two questions. Firstly, what are the chronicles of university supervisors on school mentors' support to student teachers during teaching practice? Secondly, how do university supervisors view the mentors' support to student teachers during teaching practice?

Method

This paper entailed qualitative research design which applied a directed document analysis of the content in the evaluation reports of university supervisors. The document analysis is a form of qualitative research whereby documents are interpreted by the researcher to give voice and meaning to the topic studied. Document analysis incorporates coding of the content into themes in a similar way as a focus group or interview transcripts are analysed. This technique is mostly used to gather required information and is very useful when stakeholders are not available to give the required information.

The study was conducted in South Africa, King Cetshwayo District. This area is dominated by rural schools where learners travel long distances to schools by foot; roads are gravelled, water is a challenge in most areas, most parents cannot read and write and schools are supported by pensioners. In such an impoverished environment, student teachers cannot naturally imbibe a professional disposition without a purposeful interaction with experienced mentors. In this setting, even most learners are demotivated to learn since they hardly look up to community members who are professionals and literate. Dealing with such learners may be a challenge for student teachers who are still inexperienced but expected to deal with them, hence school mentors' support is a dire need.

The population for this study were university supervisors during teaching practice period; 14 evaluation reports were purposively sampled. The reports that were used were those that had elaborated relevantly and clearly on how school mentors supported student teachers. After securing 14 evaluation reports from university supervisors, the data were coded and themes developed to ease analysis. The following five ethical principles were upheld during the collection of the data: respect for privacy and autonomy, reciprocity, freedom of scientific enquiry, attribution, and the respect for intellectual property. Consequently, university protocols were observed from requesting the records up to analysing the data without divulging supervisors' personal details.

Results and Discussion

Positive Support from School Mentors

This section discusses the findings that unfolded from the analysis of data. The support from school mentors to student teachers was in line with Stanulis, Little and Wibbens (2012) who argue that school mentors are expected to offer student teachers professional and pedagogical support. This may suggest that these school mentors were clear about their attributes as mentors. In other words, they knew how to help others learn to teach (Hobson, Ashby, Malderez & Tomlinson, 2009) and 'others' being student teachers who need to learn to facilitate teaching and learning activities. It means that these school mentors understood the meaning of 'teach

about teaching' (Leatham & Peterson, 2010). This suggests that school mentors supported student teachers in practising and acquiring knowledge, beliefs and skills that could enable them to teach well (Jaspers et al., 2014). Therefore, some school mentors fulfilled one of their roles and responsibilities of providing support for student teachers.

When school mentors offered classes to student teachers to practise the art of teaching, they showed a good sign of working in parallel with student teachers as more experienced colleagues (Lamb et al., 2016); working together with student teachers is one of the attributes of a good mentor. This may mean that school mentors were prepared to observe and give feedback to student teachers about their teaching. In other words, school mentors were prepared to work in tandem with student teachers during teaching practice. This suggests that most school mentors were willing to help student teachers sharpen their teaching skills and abilities through practice. This may have been of great help to student teachers who were looking for a chance to prepare themselves for evaluation while developing professional teaching skills. As student teachers got a chance to practise teaching, they might have been able to develop their sense of efficacy (Moulding et al., 2014) which could make them competent teachers. Furthermore, student teachers may have received expert advice, guidance and set of worthwhile alternatives to teaching (Maphosa & Ndamba, 2012) that they needed from school mentors thus developing professionally (Mukeredzi, 2017).

As school mentors prepared student teachers for evaluation, they were aware that they should be involved and concerned with the evaluation of student teachers and learning (Feiman-Nemser, 2012); hence they wanted to know how student teachers performed during evaluation. This shows full support from school mentors which concur with investing some effort and time in student teachers (Jaeger, Bertot & Gorham, 2015; Hochberg et al. 2015). This shows how much school mentors cared about student teachers in terms of how they had developed their pedagogic literacy (Lamb et al., 2016). The interest also on debriefing sessions shows how school mentors took teamwork and student teachers' motivation (Schatz-Oppenheimer, 2017) seriously. It means that some schools mentors were committed to knowing about the professional development of student teachers they were mentoring and guiding so that they could identify difficulties (Crasborn, 2010) they experienced during lesson presentation. In other words, these school mentors were willing to offer what (Gardiner & Weisling, 2016) refer to as "out-side the action" type of educative mentoring which encapsulates debriefing sessions. This was a symbol of commitment to a joint venture between the school mentor and the university supervisor in assisting the student teachers to develop a teaching profession and Mtika et al. (2014) refer to this as essential social interaction between the school mentor and the university supervisor for the benefit of student teachers.

It can be deduced from the above arguments that the views from university supervisors revealed that some school mentors offer the required support to student teachers. The type of support they referred to was the allocation of classes, preparing student teachers for evaluation and interest in debriefing sessions after evaluation. However, university supervisors did not give more details on what school mentors did or were expected to do after allocating classes to student teachers. This suggests that university supervisors were not as vivid in that aspect. On the contrary, scholars argued that student teachers need professional and pedagogical support which university supervisors did not emphasise as an aspect that requires the involvement of school mentors during class visits. University supervisors did not also talk about knowledge and skills acquisition as part of the support needed by student teachers from school mentors. It is possible that university supervisors did not guide school mentors about steps to take after allocating classes to student teachers. This was not peculiar from the views of scholars because they only argued that school mentors knew how to teach and they taught about teaching but did not explain essential aspects to be taught when teaching.

Furthermore, university supervisors noted that school mentors prepared student teachers for evaluation but did not get into details of the issues that school mentors dealt with while preparing student teachers. School mentors did not allude to the significance of preparing student teachers for evaluation. According to scholars, preparing student teachers for evaluation shows the working together between the school mentors and student teachers. University supervisors did not touch base with pedagogical literacy that student teachers need during teaching practice. Also, university supervisors did not allude to why school mentors were amenable to debriefing sessions. In other words, it is unclear why school mentors had an interest in the feedback from university supervisors after student teachers' evaluations.

Negative Support from School Mentors

The views from university supervisors indicated that most school mentors did not support student teachers. This lack of support from school mentors deprived student teachers a make-up for discrepancies that might have arisen from the dearth of knowledge and skills acquired via teacher educators (Polikoff et al., 2015). This suggests that student teachers need this support from school mentors since the knowledge and skills acquired at

the higher education institution are not adequate until they have been exposed to the real situation under the guidance of school mentors. The inability of school mentors to support student teachers defeated the purpose of sending student teachers for teaching practice so that they could receive mentoring from experienced subject teachers. Without the mentoring exercise, school mentors as experienced teachers did not allow student teachers who were inexperienced to engage in mutual learning (Van Ginkel et al., 2016). One of the reasons for not supporting student teachers, according to university supervisors, was that school mentors do not have time for student teachers. In line with this, (Tirivanhu, 2014) argues that the curriculum for school mentors is congested hence they have little time to supervise student teachers. If school mentors were willing to support student teachers, they would have made time to do that. Therefore, the chances of student teachers developing professionally were very slim.

School mentors might have been aware of critical issues that were expected from student teachers during evaluation as well as for their professional development. It is not clear though why they did not promote and support student teachers' awareness about these issues that inform the teaching profession and help them learn about teaching profession (Agudo & de Dios, 2016). The failure to support student teachers was not peculiar since (Tirivanhu, 2014) argue that some school-based mentors do not assist the student teachers to develop teaching or pedagogical skills. The reason could be that they are not trained to support student teachers (Sethusha, 2014). The inability to support student teachers may have a serious bearing on their performance and development as professional teachers. School mentors should provide the necessary support to student teachers so that they may become good and competent teachers.

It is inexplicable that school mentors dumped their work on student teachers without supporting them. It was a clear indication that school mentors were unwilling to mentor support student teachers. This was a violation of one of the aims of the student-teacher/mentor relationship which is to transmit knowledge, skills, attitudes, and culture regarding the student teacher's career choice (Jones, Kelsey & Brown, 2014). In other words, school mentors regarded the presence of student teachers as their chance not do their job. This is in contrast to the practices for effective student-teacher mentoring which is not simply leaving student teachers alone, turning on the commentary track, working jointly to find creative outlets, modelling lessons and new learning content, joint planning (Clark & Byrnes, 2012) for both student teachers and school mentors and making time to talk, connecting the student teachers to the larger school political world and treating teaching practice as a learning opportunity (Larkin, 2013). Dumping the work on student teachers could have resulted to some student teachers not getting a chance to acquire the benefits of a good relationship emanating from working together with school mentors. This suggests that student teachers "were not provided opportunities to observe their school-based mentors teaching" (Tirivanhu, 2014, p.1480).

It was also very disheartening that some school mentors did not offer their support because they are not paid to support student teachers. In other words, they did not support student teachers just because they would not be paid for that since it was not part of their job description to mentor student teachers. However, it has been a concern from school mentors that the government, tertiary institutions and schools do not pay them for assisting student teachers during teaching practice (Tirivanhu, 2014). This also interfered with the theory adopted in this article which accentuates that the mentor guides the learners in discovering hidden knowledge (Maslow, 1968).

What can be gleaned from the foregoing section is that the unwillingness of school mentors to support student teachers may have deprived student teachers a chance to acquire some experiences, as per humanistic theory. Again, student teachers may have lost the opportunity to fill up the gaps emanating from the knowledge they acquired from their teacher educators. Also, school mentors as experienced teachers may have denied student teachers engagement in mutual learning which is also incumbent for teaching practice. The claim of university supervisors that school mentors do not have time for student teachers may have been an indication that school mentors were not eager to support student teachers. This unwillingness to support student teachers is contrary to one of the scholars who argued that due to the curriculum and the work-load, school mentors have little time to support student teachers. In other words, student teachers did not want to play their role in the professional learning process of student teachers, otherwise they would have made time.

As school mentors dumped their work on student teachers without any support, they did not assist the student teachers to develop their pedagogical skills, which is one of the aims of teaching practice. This action also did not enable school mentors to transmit knowledge, skills, attitudes, and culture regarding the student teacher's career choice. It may mean that school mentors did not treat teaching practice as a learning opportunity for student teachers, otherwise they would have given them a dutyload and thereafter guide them accordingly. The failure of school mentors to pay close attention to critical issues of evaluation may be deemed as a failure to guide student teachers well in discovering hidden knowledge. School mentors refused to support student

teachers because they were not paid to do that; unfortunately, that had nothing to do with student teachers. School mentors were supposed to support student teachers by referring their concerns to the relevant bodies.

Conclusion

This paper concludes that some school mentors are willing to assist student teachers through guidance and support and, they understand their responsibilities and significance of mentoring. It also concludes that some school mentors are not willing to offer their support since they will not be paid for the support they offer. Furthermore, school mentors need to improve their mentoring skills hence they do not understand the critical areas of student evaluation and mentoring at large. This paper also concludes that some school mentors simply dump their work on student teachers without any guidance. Worthy of note among the voices of university supervisors is the absence of any reference to the self, that is, the agency of teacher educators. Distancing oneself from the phenomenon of interest appears to be the adopted defence mechanism, and this dissipates the institutional responsibility of a coordinated mentorship into a peripheral scope.

Recommendations

This paper recommends that school mentors be given incentives so that they can undertake the task of supporting student teachers freely. School mentors need to be workshopped about their roles and responsibilities. HEIs should identify school mentors who are willing to mentor support student teachers. School mentors should be made aware of the significance and importance of mentoring so that they put their weight on it.

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